

Resident Evil: Twenty Years of Virtual Horror (Updated for its 30th Anniversary in 2026)

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The year 2016 was undoubtedly a year of anniversaries and celebrations, as yet another major video game series joined the list. If we recently discussed the anniversary of Pokémon, today it is the turn of Resident Evil—whose original Japanese title is Biohazard (バイオハザード)—which celebrated its twentieth anniversary in 2016 and its thirtieth in 2026. In the future I intend to write more extensive and detailed entries about the series, continuing the work I began years ago on my personal blog; for now, however, I will focus on the most essential aspects of Resident Evil.

Capcom released the first Resident Evil in 1996

March 22 marks the anniversary of Resident Evil, the date on which the first game began its journey into the hall of fame of the video game world, launching the franchise in 1996. Sony's PlayStation was the first console to receive the title—followed later by PC and Sega Saturn—which provided a major boost to Capcom after its remarkable success. As of February 2026, the franchise has sold approximately 183 million copies worldwide.

While it is true that the horror genre was already present in video games—with notable examples such as *Sweet Home* (1989), also developed by Capcom, which was released the same day as its film adaptation; or *Alone in the Dark* (1992), the first horror adventure to feature three-dimensional graphics (though not stereoscopic 3D), along with its sequels—it was *Resident Evil* that popularised the zombie phenomenon within video games. Earlier titles had already laid the foundations for what would later become known as the *survival horror* genre.

These games typically draw on themes from horror literature, combining them with elements of adventure and exploration. The genre is characterised by protagonists who must confront creatures —such as zombies, monsters or mutated creatures— with very limited resources and weaponry, creating situations of constant tension and shock for the player. Although *Resident Evil* was not the first game that would later be classified under this label, the term *survival horror* itself was coined by Capcom as a marketing slogan for the game and, following its success, eventually became the standard designation for this type of video game.

Sweet Home can in fact be considered the true precursor of *Resident Evil*, as it already included elements such as the setting of a mansion filled with horrors and mysteries for the player to solve —placing them in a state of constant uncertainty until the story gradually unfolds— along with puzzles and even the famous door-opening scenes later popularised in the first *Resident Evil*. Capcom itself has acknowledged this influence and, fortunately for the future of the franchise, returned to this earlier inspiration in later years, especially in light of the direction the series has taken in its more recent releases, including several remakes of the original games.

Shinji Mikami, the creator of the series and its most visible figure until leaving Capcom in 2007, always sought to translate the emotions experienced by the protagonists of George Andrew Romero’s zombie and horror films into the medium of video games. After admiring works such as *Alone in the Dark*, he decided to create *Biohazard* (*Resident Evil*). Mikami would later also become one of the individuals responsible for other franchises such as *Dino Crisis* and *Ace Attorney*. He worked closely with Hideki Kamiya, who served as system planner for this first *Resident Evil*, later directed *Resident Evil 2*, contributed as a designer on *Resident Evil 0*, and would go on to create *Viewtiful Joe* and *Devil May Cry* —the last one, originally conceived as a *Resident Evil* project— and, after leaving Capcom, the *Bayonetta* series.

Dante, the protagonist of the *Devil May Cry* series —on which both Shinji Mikami and Hideki Kamiya collaborated— first appeared in the original instalment released for the PlayStation 2 in 2001. To his right is Bayonetta, the protagonist of the eponymous franchise, whose first title was released in 2010 for PlayStation 3 and Xbox 360. The game was later reissued for Wii U and Nintendo Switch alongside its sequel —exclusive to those platforms since its release in 2014— and a third instalment, released exclusively for Nintendo Switch in 2022.

Bayonetta and its second and third instalments were developed by PlatinumGames—a studio also known for titles such as *NieR: Automata*—which over the years has included former Capcom members such as Shinji Mikami and Hideki Kamiya. *Bayonetta* was conceived, in part, as a response to Capcom: an attempt to demonstrate that a new action game reminiscent of the early Devil May Cry titles in which they had participated could still bring freshness to the *hack and slash* genre—video games characterised by frenetic combat combined with elements of adventure and exploration.

Returning to *Resident Evil*, the game also reflects a broader Japanese cultural anxiety regarding war, human self-destruction, and the dangers inherent in humanity's attempts to “play God”, particularly in relation to radiation and biological warfare. The zombies and other grotesque creatures that populate the Resident Evil series are the result of mutations caused by viruses and parasitic organisms.

Mikami intended for players to confront the undead directly and to experience the tension themselves, forcing them to make decisions rather than merely passively consuming images and sound, as in cinema. Unfortunately, Capcom gradually moved away from the original design philosophy of the early instalments, and over the past decades subsequent entries in the Resident Evil series have experienced significant fluctuations in quality, despite continuing to produce notable titles, as will be discussed later.

The first *Resident Evil* transported players—through a live-action introductory sequence that can easily be described as “iconic”, “cult”, and distinctly “B-movie” in tone, owing to its modest production values and clear homage to low-budget horror cinema—to the seemingly abandoned Spencer Mansion and its surrounding grounds. This location would ultimately prove to be the central source of the game's narrative and the catalyst for the events explored in later Resident Evil titles. The original *Resident Evil* represented a successful gamble on Capcom's part, captivating players through its memorable protagonists—including the imposing figure of Albert Wesker, who would later emerge as the principal antagonist of the series—its compelling narrative background, and its distinctive gameplay mechanics, high level of difficulty, cinematic presentation, and striking visual style.

The game also introduced an additional layer of difficulty, as its controls were somewhat challenging to master. Because the game utilised a graphical engine built upon pre-rendered backgrounds and fixed camera angles, character movement differed significantly from the more intuitive control systems typical of contemporary games. Healing items, save points—the iconic typewriters and their limited ink ribbons—and ammunition were all scarce resources, continually prolonging the player's sense of tension throughout the experience.

From the moment the protagonists' companions—members of a special rescue team—are dispatched to the outskirts of Raccoon City to investigate a series of murders and subsequently disappear, to the gradual revelation of the full story surrounding the Spencer Mansion, its numerous traps and enemies, the narrative twists, and the infamous Umbrella Corporation and its criminal activities, the game maintained a powerful sense of atmosphere that captivated players of the time. The ending itself varied depending on how many teammates the player managed to rescue during the course of the adventure.

The game later received a remake for the Nintendo GameCube in 2002, which was subsequently re-released for modern consoles in 2015, as well as for PC.

Chris Redfield and Jill Valentine, the protagonists of *Resident Evil* and the two playable characters available in the original game, as depicted in the 2015 PC version of the GameCube remake of *Resident Evil*

In addition, the game received a Nintendo DS edition —*Resident Evil: Deadly Silence* (2006)— released to commemorate the franchise’s tenth anniversary, as well as a remastered version that has since appeared on several gaming platforms, the first of which was released in Japan in 2014. The Nintendo DS version made use of the console’s touchscreen controls and introduced new modes, including multiplayer functionality, microphone usage, and additional gameplay mechanics.

Resident Evil continued to expand thereafter

Capcom had already planned to develop a second instalment. By this point, Shinji Mikami had been promoted from planner to producer. *Resident Evil 2*, directed by Hideki Kamiya and produced by Mikami, was released in 1998, at a time when the franchise had already achieved worldwide recognition. The game also featured contributions from the artist Dai-chan, who had collaborated on other Capcom franchises such as *Street Fighter* and *Darkstalkers*.

Resident Evil 2 has appeared on numerous consoles as well as on PC, and remains one of the most beloved entries among fans of the series. It was also, for a time, the best-selling title in the franchise —excluding later re-releases and alternative versions— with six million copies sold, a figure later surpassed by *Resident Evil 5*. A remake of the game was released in 2019 for several systems, including PlayStation 4 and 5, Xbox One and Xbox Series X and S, Nintendo Switch, and PC.

For this second instalment, set two months after the events of the original game, Mikami opted to introduce an entirely new cast of characters rather than reuse the previous protagonists. Players could therefore control either Leon Scott Kennedy—a rookie police officer in Raccoon City—or Claire Redfield, a secondary school student who travels to Raccoon City in search of her missing brother Chris, the protagonist of the first *Resident Evil* alongside Jill Valentine.

By this point, rats had spread the T-virus (Tyrant Virus)—the agent responsible for the grotesque mutations seen in the first game—throughout Raccoon City, triggering a full-scale outbreak of the undead. Leon, as he himself remarks, could hardly have imagined a more dramatic first day on the job as a police officer.

Left: Leon Scott Kennedy, from *Resident Evil 2* (1998). Right: official artwork by Dai-chan for *Super Street Fighter II* (1993).

In *Resident Evil 2*, the choice of character did not merely determine who the player controlled, but also which path they would take, as selecting Claire or Leon provided a different perspective on the same events. Completing the game with the initially chosen character would unlock the alternate path for the other protagonist. This instalment also introduced Ada Wong, an undercover agent who deceives Leon into assisting her mission. Their relationship remains ambiguous, with it unclear whether Ada genuinely develops feelings for Leon or merely exploits him.

Actions taken during the first playthrough influence the subsequent experience with the other character, unlocking areas inaccessible if that character were chosen first. This game also established enduring series mechanics, such as displaying the protagonist's remaining health through on-screen animations—e.g., clutching the abdomen when injured—and the iconic Game Over screens, which depict the grisly deaths of the characters if the player fails.

The success of the series brought more titles and radical changes

Resident Evil 3: Nemesis was released in 1999, with much of its story taking place the day before the events of *Resident Evil 2*, continuing into the following day. Players assume the role of Jill Valentine, seeking to escape the zombies of Raccoon City, while facing an even greater threat: Nemesis. This bioweapon relentlessly pursues the player throughout the adventure, introducing a heightened sense of tension—similar in concept to Mr. X from the original *Resident Evil 2*, although far more persistent in the remake. The game also allowed players to make decisions that affected the storyline.

Subsequent entries included important secondary titles, such as *Code: Veronica* (2000, Dreamcast) and *Resident Evil Zero* (2002, GameCube). While these retained the series' core features—camera angles, control style, and survival horror mechanics—spin-offs diverged significantly, including shooting-focused games like *Resident Evil Survivor*. In 2005, Mikami shifted the franchise's direction, ultimately completing *Resident Evil 4*, marking a turning point for the series.

***Resident Evil 4* represented a complete franchise overhaul**

Today, *Resident Evil 4* is the most widely recognised and influential entry in the series among general audiences, though not necessarily the highest-selling. It remains a celebrated title for GameCube, and later PlayStation 2, PC, Wii, and other platforms, distinguished by its numerous re-releases and remasters.

Mikami and his team introduced new control schemes, which significantly improved playability, creating a faster-paced and more intuitive experience compared to previous titles. However, this shift also brought changes to camera mechanics, moving away from fixed pre-rendered viewpoints to an over-the-shoulder perspective, enabled by the technical capabilities of contemporary consoles. This transition allowed for more enemies, increased variety, and more complex player interactions, delivering a gameplay experience with greater action, intensity, and spectacle than prior entries.

Despite these changes, *Resident Evil 4* retained survival horror elements, balancing action, horror sequences, and puzzles. After Mikami and the Clover Studio team departed from Capcom, the franchise gradually shifted toward action-oriented gameplay, emphasising combat over fear, marking a new era for the series.

Leon faces El Gigante (Spanish for “The Giant”), a boss at the end of a level in *Resident Evil 4* —screenshot taken from the 2014 HD version for PC. The wolf depicted can be assisted by the player to escape from a trap; if freed, it aids in this encounter by distracting the enemy.

It should be noted that its setting was rather absurd, sending our hero Leon Scott Kennedy to a supposed Spain where all inhabitants live in the middle of the forest in cabins and speak Latin American Spanish —the only characters speaking with a genuine Spanish accent are those who actually speak English, such as Saddler, one of the main antagonists of the title. Leon and Ada Wong reunite in this instalment, and their relationship remains precarious.

To the dismay of the most devoted fans, the enemies in *Resident Evil 4* are not zombies —no similar foes appear— but humans infected by a parasite known as “Las Plagas,” (Spanish for “The Plagues”) controlled by the primary antagonist, Osmund Saddler. Nevertheless, *Resident Evil 4* is considered an excellent game, even by series enthusiasts, being one of the longest, most replayable, addictive, and content-rich entries in the franchise.

Thus, in 2009, already without the original *Resident Evil* team or its creators, *Resident Evil 5* was released for PlayStation 3, Xbox 360, and PC, featuring a hyper-muscular Chris Redfield, battling hordes of enemies in African landscapes. The game reintroduces Albert Wesker, only to dismiss him in a somewhat underwhelming manner. This title represented a true disappointment for fans, who saw the franchise’s future as bleak, believing Capcom had diluted the series to make it more accessible to a broader, less demanding audience.

That said, the game boasts impressive graphics for its time, strong atmosphere, and outstanding performance thanks to Capcom’s MT Framework engine. As an action game, it is quite enjoyable, particularly due to its cooperative mode —one player controlling Chris and the other Sheva Alomar, Chris’s partner in this adventure.

Recent entries and the franchise’s future

Resident Evil 5 was followed by pure shooting games, such as the Chronicles series for Wii, with two releases in 2007 and 2009, and later *Resident Evil: The Mercenaries 3D* —based on a “mini-game” unlockable in certain main entries, essentially focused on defeating hordes of zombies in the shortest time possible. While not poor titles, they did not offer fans experiences reminiscent of the earlier adventures.

However, Capcom did not completely ignore fan requests —complaints from fans had been ongoing since shortly after the release of *Resident Evil 4*— and in 2012 they delivered a truly strong entry: *Resident Evil: Revelations*. This game returned to a more classic approach, retaining modern control and camera schemes while bringing back the horror experience that had been sorely missed, though not quite reaching the level of the original episodes.

All of this was achieved on a handheld console, the Nintendo 3DS —a virtually indispensable title for the system— which delivered almost incredible graphics given the hardware limitations. Later, *Revelations* was also released on other platforms, including PC, Xbox 360, PlayStation 3, and Wii U.

Jill Valentine confronts multiple enemies —BOWs, or Bio-Organic Weapons— in *Resident Evil: Revelations*.
Screenshot taken from the 2013 PC version.

Such releases tend to produce mixed feelings, as they offer hope that Capcom has not entirely forgotten how to make Resident Evil more than just a cash cow; however, later the same year, the company returned to familiar patterns with *Resident Evil 6* and *Operation Raccoon City* —both from 2012— titles that once again focused on action rather than survival horror.

With few honourable exceptions, such as certain sections of Leon Scott Kennedy's campaign in *Resident Evil 6* —returning as a playable character alongside his new partner, Helena Harper— or Ada Wong's segments, which contained some acceptable horror and survival elements, the game largely departed from the classic style of the franchise.

Resident Evil 6 was fundamentally an action game with monsters rather than a true horror experience. Chris Redfield or Sherry Birkin were relegated to facing endless hordes of enemies with near-infinite ammunition, removing virtually all traces of survival horror —no puzzles, no exploration, all corridors with a single predetermined path for the player— accompanied by explosions and swarms of enemies converging on the protagonists. *Operation Raccoon City* did little to improve matters, being a game entirely focused on shooting.

In 2015, *Resident Evil: Revelations 2* was released for PC, PS Vita, PlayStation 3 and 4, Xbox 360 and One, allowing players to control Claire Redfield once again, as well as Barry Burton —a character from the first *Resident Evil*— to rescue his daughter Moira in an episodic adventure. While not a bad game, it fails to capture the true spirit of the series —its episodic structure, initially released in separate parts, did little to improve fans' perception of the title— and it is oriented more towards action than survival, with virtually no moments of genuine terror throughout the experience.

Resident Evil has also extended into cinema, with a series of live-action films starring Milla Jovovich —whose character, Alice, was created specifically for the films— which, unfortunately, were only loosely related to the games' plots and were not particularly remarkable, despite moderate commercial success; the last of these, *The Final Chapter*, premiered in 2017. The franchise underwent a reboot in 2021 with *Resident Evil: Welcome to Raccoon City*, and another reboot followed in 2026, due to the poor commercial and critical reception of the previous reboot, as well as the 2022 Netflix series, which was cancelled after its first season.

Additionally, in 2008 and 2012, two 3D-animated films inspired by the franchise were released: *Resident Evil: Degeneration* —with Leon and Claire as main characters— and *Damnation* —featuring Leon and Ada as protagonists— both set within the games' continuity and largely accepted by fans as canon. This was followed by *Vendetta* in 2017, featuring Leon, Chris, and Rebecca Chambers, marking the debut of the franchise's animated universe. *Infinite Darkness* (2021), available on Netflix, depicts events occurring between *Resident Evil 4* and *5*, following Leon during his years as an agent, while also exploring Claire's adventures since *Code: Veronica* and the *Degeneration* film. These were followed by *Death Island* in 2023, which reunites Chris, Jill, and Leon, paying homage to several of the animated films and key games in the series.

The franchise has not been limited to adaptations for cinema and series; it has also produced a considerable amount of merchandise, including comics, novels inspired by the games or narrating alternative events, collectible figures —particularly those by NECA and, more prominently, Hot Toys, renowned for hyper-realistic scale models— and numerous editions and reissues of its soundtracks, notably the outstanding *Biohazard Orchestra* album (1999), compiling music from the first three Resident Evil games performed live in Japan.

20th Anniversary Events

In 2016, Capcom released *Resident Evil: Umbrella Corps*, an action-focused, multiplayer-oriented spin-off where teams of combatants face off on battlefields with various objectives, alongside zombies and other classic enemies from the series. As a non-canonical title, it revisited familiar characters and locations from the franchise. It was released in May of that year to commemorate *Resident Evil*'s anniversary.

Screenshot of the PC version of *Resident Evil: Umbrella Corps*

Something materialised, beyond a commemorative website, in the form of the first of a series of videos that the company uploaded to the YouTube platform, featuring interviews with members of the Resident Evil team to celebrate the franchise's anniversary. The first of these was an interview with Hiroyuki Kobayashi, one of the current producers of Resident Evil, who began his career as a programmer on the franchise's very first title—and has also participated in the animated Resident Evil films and in video game series such as Devil May Cry, Dino Crisis, and Sengoku Basara. The interview can be viewed following this link.

The franchise since then

Following the 20th anniversary, Resident Evil entered one of the most interesting—and paradoxically most coherent—phases in its history. Capcom, aware of the fatigue caused by the franchise's excessive shift towards action, opted for a conceptual return to its origins: reinstating fear, vulnerability, and atmosphere as central pillars of the experience. In other words, a return to survival horror.

This change manifested decisively in *Resident Evil 7: Biohazard* (2017), a title that broke with many of the series' conventions by adopting a first-person perspective, introducing a new protagonist—Ethan Winters—and a storyline seemingly disconnected from the main narrative arcs. Yet beneath this new veneer, the game recaptured sensations very close to those of the original *Resident Evil*: confined spaces, limited resources, careful exploration, and a constant tension that reinstated terror as the primary focus.

Its critical and commercial success confirmed that this was the correct path. A review of this title can be accessed following this link.

Concurrently, Capcom initiated an ambitious programme of remakes, not limited to mere technical upgrades, but reinterpreting the classics with deep respect for their original essence. The first of these was *Resident Evil 2* (2019), an exemplary work that successfully modernised mechanics, narrative, and presentation without betraying the spirit of the 1998 original. This was followed by *Resident Evil 3* in 2020—more controversial due to its shorter length—and, years later, *Resident Evil 4* in 2023, which reimagined one of the most influential games in the medium with tonal and narrative maturity appropriate for contemporary audiences.

The main series continued with *Resident Evil Village* (2021), a direct sequel to the seventh instalment, which combined intimate horror with action elements inherited from previous eras, functioning almost as a compendium of what *Resident Evil* has been over three decades. Vampires, werewolves, and gothic castles coexisted here with laboratories, biological mutations, and the eternal backdrop of unchecked human experimentation.

By 2026, *Resident Evil* reached its 30th anniversary not as an exhausted franchise, but as a series that has successfully reinterpreted its own legacy, acknowledged past missteps, and reinvented itself without losing its identity. This was evident in 2026 with the release of the next mainline entry, *Resident Evil Requiem*, coinciding with the franchise's 30th anniversary, and with the announcement of remakes of *Code: Veronica* and *Resident Evil 0*.

Thirty years after that lost mansion on the outskirts of Raccoon City, survival horror remains alive, demonstrating that well-constructed fear does not age: it evolves. Through this franchise, Capcom has delivered a lesson on whether companies should listen to their fans, resulting in both commercially successful titles and games of outstanding quality, proving that commercial appeal and high quality can coexist.

Sources

- **Consulted texts:** Capcom Database, Resident Evil.net, Steam, Engadget.com, Templo de Sephiroth, Polygon.com, *Resident Evil: Pandemia* | **Text authored by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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